

Milestone: M3.4 The B1MG data analysis challenge call

Lead Participant:

CRG

Author:

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Due:

30 Nov 2021

Date Of Completion:

29 Nov 2021

Means of Verification

See [M3.4 The B1MG data analysis challenge call - Evidence](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes

The data analysis challenge will be conducted during 2022 as planned. We are currently in the process of sourcing samples and preparing the MTAs. The work delay was due to the pandemic.

Project participants & others

University of Oslo, Hartwig Medical Foundation, KU Leuven, DKFZ, FIMM University of Helsinki, Scilife Lab, Laboratoire National de Santé (LNS), Carlos III Institute of Health, University of Verona, Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre, Danish National Genome Center, Fundación Pública Galega de Medicina Xenómica, Radboud UMC, Universidade de Aveiro

Next action steps

Sequence the four tumor-normal samples, generate their gold set of variants, distribute data files to laboratories for analysis and conduct the interlaboratory challenge during 2022, as planned.

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